

Influence of modified urea and placement on N use in irrigated rice

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Numerous N response experiments have shown that fertilizer N recovery by rice is seldom higher than 30-40%; even with the best agronomic practices and strictly controlled conditions, recovery seldom exceeds 60-65%. Using urea supergranules (USG) or urea briquettes, deep placed, has increased N efficiency, and crop response to sulfur-coated urea (SCU) has generally been superior to response to urea in a single dose and often to split applications.

We compared the efficiency of SCU, USG, and best split urea at different N levels in a randomized block design with four replications. The 4-yr experiment (1981-84) used medium-duration Asha and Usha as test varieties. Soil was a Vertisol, clay loam texture, with pH 7.0, 1.3% organic matter, 11% total N, and CEC 33 meq/100 g. Exchange-

Grain yield with different modified urea materials, placement techniques, and nitrogen levels. Raipur, India (1981-84 wet seasons).

N(kg/ha)	Urea form ^a	Grain yield(t/ha)				
		1981	1982	1983	1984	Mean
0	-	2.0	2.6	1.9	2.0	2.1
29	PU	2.3	3.1	2.7	-	2.7
58	PU	2.4	3.6	3.0	3.9	3.2
87	PU	2.8	3.4	3.4	4.4	3.5
116	PU	2.9	3.9	3.7	4.4	3.7
Mean	PU	2.6	3.5	3.2	4.2	3.4
29	SCU	2.6	3.3	3.2	-	3.0
58	SCU	3.1	4.0	3.8	4.0	3.7
87	SCU	3.2	4.0	4.2	4.2	3.9
116	SCU	3.7	4.4	4.5	4.5	4.3
Mean	SCU	3.2	3.9	3.9	4.3	3.8
29	USG	2.4	3.6	3.2	-	3.1
58	USG	2.7	3.6	3.7	4.3	3.6
87	USG	2.8	4.1	4.1	4.6	3.9
116	USG	3.1	3.6	4.3	4.8	4.0
Mean	USG	2.7	3.7	3.8	4.6	3.7
LSD (0.05)		0.4	0.7	0.4	2.6	
CV (%)		9.5	11.2	7.2	10.5	

^aPU was applied as best split, SCU was broadcast and incorporated, USG was placed 10-12cm deep in the soil

able bases (in meq/100 g) were 0.07 Na, 0.63 K, 4.7 Mg, and 27 Ca. Available P was 17 ppm by Bray method and 4 ppm by Olsen. Available Zn was 2.7 ppm.

Maximum yields at all N levels were obtained with SCU broadcast and incorporated, followed by USG placed

10-12 cm deep, and prilled urea (PU) best split (see table). Yields increased with increased N.

Highest N use efficiency was 32.1 kg grain/kg N as USG at 29 kg N/ha. Averaged over N levels, maximum N use efficiency was 18.7 kg grain/kg N as SCU. ■

Influence of modified urea materials at different N rates on estimated wetland rice soil ammonium-N and nitrate-N

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Changes in $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$ and $\text{NO}_3^-\text{-N}$ levels in wetland soil can provide valuable insights into N losses and availability of N for rice. The $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$ and $\text{NO}_3^-\text{-N}$ at 0-15 cm depth in flooded soil were measured at 15, 30, 45, and 60 d after transplanting (DT).

The experimental area was Aquic Hapludoll (Mollisol of Tarai moist plains region about 30 km south of the foothills of the Shivalik Range of the Himalayas). Soil was silt loam with pH 7.9, 1.2% organic C, 0.1% total N, 8 ppm available

1. $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$ content in soil as influenced by N rates (a) and sources (b).